

THE CONCEPT OF FAMILY LAW AND THE LEGAL PROVISION OF PROTECTION OF FAMILY RELATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: this article covers the concept of family law, the essence of its content, family relations with scientific and legal foundations.

Keywords: family law, family relationships, harmonious generation, Family Institute, marriage, registry office, couple relations, upbringing, with many children.

Today, the issue of raising a young and harmonious generation in our Republic has risen to the level of Public Policy. Because the perfect generation is the future of our homeland and the continuation of our lineage. To educate them as modern, perfect people, to instill in their minds our national-cultural, spiritual values, to arm themselves with our ancient and rich history, to mentally and spiritually competently educate them is an urgent matter of our day. In narrowing the solution to this issue, the self-governing body of citizens has received the name of a small society within the society-the family has its own role.

Our President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev's decision on June 27, 2018 "on approval of the concept of strengthening the Family Institute in the Republic of Uzbekistan" approved the priorities and implementation measures of the concept. Measures for the implementation of this concept are established, which provide for the creation of a single interagency information base of the "Family" Center with the aim of improving the institutional and legal framework for strengthening the family institution, strengthening social partnership, timely obtaining information about families with difficult living conditions.¹

Also not overlooked are the further development of family business, the system of providing social services to families, the identification of the family code criteria for responsibility of family legal relations, the establishment of alimony, the further improvement of the norms on the protection of women and children's rights at the time of divorce, the provision of preferential loans (mortgages, consumption, etc.) to

The concept also emphasized the issue of improving the system of pre-marital medical examinations, strengthening measures to prevent early and cousin marriages, the birth of children with birth defects.

The document also focuses on social protection, providing assistance to single and multi-child parents who are raising children with minors or disabilities in the effective use of plots of land, methodological and practical manuals on the proper care and education of children with disabilities for parents, improving their skills with the help of patronage and social services, etc.

It is also envisaged to improve internal family and personal relationships in families, in particular the relationship between parents and children, husband and wife, mother-in-law

¹ Mirziyoyev Sh.M. «O'zbekiston Respublikasida oila institutini mustahkamlash konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to'g'risida"gi qarori 2018 yilning 27 iyun

and bride, to introduce mechanisms for practical resolution of conflict and difficult living conditions in the family.² Coordination and monitoring of the process of implementation of the concept and the "road map" was entrusted to the scientific and practical Research Center "Family" under the Cabinet of Ministers. Since 2019, International Family Day is celebrated in Uzbekistan every year on May 15. The corresponding draft of the government order will be entered into the Cabinet of Ministers until September 1 of this year. In Uzbekistan, increasing the well-being of every family and every person, strengthening the harmony of citizens, has risen to the level of Public Policy. Our First President Was I.A.Karimov spoke about his duties in this regard: "the most important task is to give birth to a folksy, righteous society. The foundation of this society is primarily made up of thousands and millions of families who are rich and wealthy, who know the value of Labor, are spiritually healthy and have a high cultural level".

The family is the result of long-lasting historical progress, an objectively necessary, integral part of the structure of society.

In the social sense, it is the Union of socially separate organized groups of people of the family, spiritual Farm, Household and other living conditions, as well as individuals with the same interests.

- The most important social functions of the family;
- Making a man;
- Raising children;
- Maturing people physically and spiritually, combining them spiritually;

Ensuring the economic and social progress of society, the OECD performs the tasks of improving the processes of demography. In the same family, the foundations of the human character, the attitude to Labor to spiritual and cultural assets are formed.

Society is interested in the idea of a strong, spiritual and morally healthy family. Therefore, he should take care of strengthening the family, assisting it in the performance of social tasks, raising children, improving the material, domestic conditions of families with children and bridesmaids.³

The right, which implies a series of activities aimed at caring for Family Children, protecting the interests of mother and child, encouraging motherhood, is an important means of strengthening family relations.

Relations between family members (property, nomulky and other) are defined by the norms of family law, which are called Family-Legal relations. The regulation of family legal institutions constitutes the subject of the Family Institute.

Family law regulates the following relationships:

- procedure and condition for marriage;
- ending the marriage and finding it invalid;
- between kin-seed and other individuals;

establishing the order and forms of raising children in the family, deprived of parental care.

² Mirziyoyev Sh.M. «O‘zbekiston Respublikasida oila institutini mustahkamlash konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida”gi qarori bilan konsepsiya 2018 yilning 27 iyun

³ Mirziyoyev Sh.M. O‘zbekiston Liberal Demokratik partiyasining 8-syezdidagi ma’ruzasi, 2016-yil 19-oktabr.

Thus, family relations refers to social relations that occur between citizens and are regulated by family legal norms.⁴

As a subject of family legal relations, spouses, parents, children, guardians and sponsors, other related seeds and legal entities involved in the resolution of one or another relationship in the field of family law, Citizens ' Association, institutions, bodies, social associations are recognized.

Actions and decisions made by the subjects of family law on moral and material values, which are attributed to family members or former members of the family, which are subject to hshloya by law, can be objects of family legal relations.

The regulation of family relations is based on the following principles:

- recognition of marriage by the state, concluded only in the bodies of the Registry Office;
- voluntary male and female marriage union;
- equal rights of husband and wife in the family;
- mutual consent resolution of family problems;

parental and state care about the maturation and well-being of children;

limit the right of citizens to the family only if it is provided for by law and does not fall out of the norm, and only if it is necessary to carry out a survey of the legal rights and interests, ethics, health of other members of the family and other citizens.

The family is protected by the state, which is promulgated in the Constitution. In the laws on Labor, citizens, economic and financial affairs, in the laws on social security, health, public education and issues, these provisions are further clarified. Family law is important in this place.⁵

Family law is a system of legal norms that regulate personal and property relations between spouses, parents and children, as well as other members of the family. As a single example, on December 20, 2022, our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his address to the Supreme Assembly and the people of Uzbekistan, paid more attention to the education system than any other sphere.

But not all family relationships are regulated by law. Most of these relationships are moral, spiritual in nature, and in their essence they cannot be regulated by right.

Family law governs relationships that are required to be traced by the state.

This law:

- determines the procedure and conditions for concluding a marriage;
- determines the circumstances and procedure for the termination (termination) of the marriage and its finding invalid;

family members: between spouses, parents and children (adoptees and adoptees), the family law regulates personal non-nominal and property relations between relatives and other martyrs in cases and in the framework of detention in Anzar in documents; forms and rules of obtaining into the family of children who are mharum from parental care;

determines the procedure for recording acts of civil status.

Thus, marriage-a set of family relations is an area in which family law must be dealt with.

Family law duties of documents:

⁴ O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oila kodeksiga sharhlar. - Toshkent: Adolat, 2000. B. 47.

⁵ Otaxo'jayev F.M. Konstitutsiya va oila. - Toshkent: O'zbekiston, 2005. B. 42

- from strengthening the family;
- from building family relationships with mutual love, trust and respect, harmony, helping each other and a sense of responsibility to all its members in front of the family;
- from not allowing any person to arbitrarily interfere with family matters;

it consists in ensuring that family members exercise their rights without hindrance and that these rights are protected.

This right includes the relationship between marriage and annulment, a relationship that arises between a married couple, between children and parents, between those who raise children and those who raise them, between other members of the family.

The family is capable of law on the issue of marriage, and competent citizens (husband and wife) are considered subjects of legal relations in the family.

According to the family law of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

- in family relationships, a woman and a man have equal rights;
- all citizens also have equal rights in a family relationship;
- Family, motherhood, fatherhood and childhood are protected by the state.

The family is the primary, main branch of society. The family is the way people live and ensure life expectancy. Its high prestige, attention and importance in society lies in the fact that in our Constitution a special chapter is dedicated to the family.

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